

List of Equipment in ICU Acharya Vinoba Bhawe , Rural Ho:

Sr.No	Device Name	Description	Cost	Annual Maintenance Cost	Working Status	Safety Check
1	PATIENT MONITOR WITH ETCO2	The end tidal CO ₂ (E'CO ₂) is the maximal partial pressure or concentration of CO ₂ in the respiratory gases at the end of an exhaled breath.				
2	SYRINGE PUMP	The purpose of using a syringe pump in clinical settings is to administer an accurate amount of drug or fluid over a relatively long duration, and it can be especially favorable for continuous infusion of very small amounts such as 0.1 ml/h				
3	INFUSION PUMP	Infusion pumps may be capable of delivering fluids in large or small amounts, and may be used to deliver nutrients or medications – such as insulin or other hormones, antibiotics, chemotherapy drugs, and pain relievers. Some infusion pumps are designed mainly for stationary use at a patient's bedside.				
4	RADIOGRAPHIC MACHINE, MOBILE	Mobile x-ray systems are often used to perform chest radiography to patients who cannot be moved to the Radiology department. As such, a mobile x-ray equipment is designed with such unique characteristics to be able to be moved within limited spaces like in between hospital beds in small wards.				
5	PULSE OXIMETER	Pulse oximetry is a test used to measure the oxygen level (oxygen saturation) of the blood. It is an easy, painless measure of how well oxygen is being sent to parts of your body furthest from your heart, such as the arms and legs.				
6	SPHYGMOMANOMETER, DIGITAL	The blood pressure device, a sphygmomanometer, is one of the most commonly used instruments in the ICU.				

- 7 BIPAP MACHINE If you have trouble breathing, a BiPap machine can help push air into your lungs. You wear a mask or nasal plugs that are connected to the ventilator. The machine supplies pressurized air into your airways. It is called “positive pressure ventilation” because the device helps open your lungs with this air pressure.
- 8 DEFIBRILLATOR OR A defibrillator is a device that gives a high energy electric shock to the heart of someone who is in cardiac arrest.
- 9 PATIENT WARMER It warms blood and IV fluids in only 30 seconds to the desired temperature. The system is suitable for all applications, from standard to high flow.
- 10 Suction APPARATUS or secretions — from a person's airway. Neonatal/pediatric intensive care ventilators provide temporary breathing support to preterm and critically ill children who require total or partial assistance to maintain adequate ventilation.
- 11 VENTILATORS, INTENSIVE CARE, NEONATAL/PEDIATRIC Give very useful information about your patient's cardiorespiratory function. This information is continuous and in 'real time' and so is especially useful in critically ill patients.
- 12 ECG MACHINE Radiant warmers are used to maintain the body temperature of newborn infants. This is best done so that the energy expended for metabolic heat production is minimized.
- 13 RADIANT WARMER
- 14 EEG SYSTEM In comatose patients the EEG can be used to assess for evidence of potentially reversible causes, such as intoxication with sedatives, NCS, and NCSE

- 15 NEONATAL INCUBATOR, TRANSPORT It is used to provide a desired warm environment to a neonate to reduce in heat loss to the environment. There are situations when a neonate or baby has to be transferred via air or road from one place to other either in search of an intensive care unit or to a different hospital for a different therapy itself.
- 16 MEDICAL GRADE MONITOR ICU provides a continuous display of not only the patient's ECG, which includes heart rate (measured as the number of QRS complexes) and rhythm, but also the oxygen saturation (SpO₂).
- 17 TOURNIQUET Tourniquets make it easier to inject. There are two ways tourniquets can help. First of all, tourniquets are used to dilate veins, making them bigger so they are easier to find and inject into.
- 18 SCLE STIMULA ICU patients can prevent ICU-AW and improve their quality of life by enhancing their muscle strength and shortening the MV duration, length of stay in the ICU and total length of stay in the hospital.
- 19 D/ FLUID WAF Blood warmers were developed to reduce the risk of hypothermia associated with the infusion of cold blood products.
- 20 HEART LUNG MACHINE It uses a machine outside the body (extracorporeal). The machine pumps the blood, provides it with oxygen and helps the body get rid of carbon dioxide.
- 21 AIR O2 BLENDER In critical care, air oxygen blenders are used to deliver a precise mixture of oxygen and air to patients who require mechanical ventilation. The device ensures that the right mixture of gases is delivered to the patient, preventing complications and improving the patient's chances of recovery.

22	FUMIGATION MACHINE	Fumigation is a process of gaseous sterilisation which is used for killing of micro-organisms and prevention of microbial growth in air, surface of wall or floor.
23	BIPAP MACHINE	A BiPap machine can help push air into your lungs. You wear a mask or nasal plugs that are connected to the ventilator. The machine supplies pressurized air into your airways.
24	INTRACRANI AL PRESSURE (ICP) MONITOR	Intracranial pressure (ICP) monitoring is used to check the pressure inside the skull of a person who has had brain injury. Injuries such as bleeding, trauma or surgery can cause the brain to swell.
25	BUBBLE CPAP	Bubble continuous positive airway pressure (bCPAP), a noninvasive respiratory support modality used to manage newborns with respiratory distress, provides continuous pressure that helps prevent derecruitment of alveoli, increasing the lungs' functional residual capacity, and thus decreasing the work of breathing.
26	ABG MACHINE	An arterial blood gas (ABG) test measures the oxygen and carbon dioxide levels in your blood as well your blood's pH balance. The sample is taken from an artery, not a vein, and healthcare providers typically order it in certain emergency situations.
27	NERVE STIMULATOR	Peripheral nerve stimulation is most commonly used for ongoing monitoring in the intensive care unit (ICU). NMBAs are used to decrease the work of breathing and facilitate mechanical ventilation in the most critically ill patients.
28	EMG MACHINE	Electromyography (EMG) measures muscle response or electrical activity in response to a nerve's stimulation of the muscle. The test is used to help detect neuromuscular abnormalities.

PAIN
MANAGEMENT
GENERATOR

The purpose of pain management is to evaluate, diagnose, and treat different types of pain. It often involves a multidisciplinary approach and includes doctors from different specialties, such as neurology and anesthesiology.

spital , Wardha

Year of utilization	Vendor provider	Vendor experience	Operator/Technician	Working experience Operator/Technician
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